

STEAMCRAFT

First Result Evaluation Report

09. July 2024.

Report

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Project Name	STEM oriented education in the virtual world with customised Minecraft modifications, STEAMCRAFT
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Introduction

The STEAMCRAFT Erasmus+ project is focused on integrating experience-oriented pedagogy, game-based learning, and sustainable energy education using Minecraft as a central tool. This report summarizes the key activities, outcomes, and next steps from the flash reports over April, May, and June. The main work packages (WPs) include project management, literature review and curriculum comparison, framework development, lesson plan development, and dissemination activities.

Summary of Key Activities and Outcomes

WP1: Project Management

April:

- The pre-kickoff and kickoff meetings were essential for setting the stage for the project. These meetings clarified administrative and financial issues and established a common repository for project documents.
- Established a Google Drive repository and prepared templates for attendance sheets and feedback forms.
- Updated Gantt chart and conducted the first online meeting with WP leaders (WPLs).
- Prepared and signed Partnership Agreements.

May:

- Conducted monthly meetings with all WPLs.
- 40% of the budget was successfully transferred to all beneficiaries. The management team also focused on updating the flash report template and communication plans based on partner feedback. This ensured alignment with project goals and responsiveness to partner needs.
- Drafted a detailed letter for the Hungarian National Authority in order to inform our main steps.

June:

- Organized another short meeting on June 17.
- Participated in an event for coordinators by the Hungarian National Authority, disseminating critical project information.
- Continued to follow the updated Gantt chart and prepared to close the M1-2-3 flash report.

Key Outcomes:

- Successful establishment of project management frameworks and financial protocols.
- Effective communication and coordination among partners.
- Ongoing monitoring and updating of project progress.

WP2: Literature Review and Curriculum Comparison

April:

- Development of the first version of instructions and Excel templates for literature review and curriculum comparison was a significant milestone. These tools standardized the process across all partners, ensuring consistent data collection.

May:

- Partners began collecting data on educational levels, student ages, and relevant literature. The standardized templates facilitated a comprehensive understanding of the project topics across different countries.
- Began the collection of data on educational levels, student ages, and relevant literature.
- The use of Slack for sharing templates and instructions ensured all partners were on the same page and could provide input and feedback efficiently.

June:

- Partners actively engaged in literature review and curriculum comparison tasks.
- Initial results indicated existing research literature focusing on project subdomains, though finding joint references for experience-oriented pedagogy, game-based learning, and sustainable energy education was more challenging.
- The lead partner, JYU, prepared to review and synthesize the collected data, aiming to create cohesive documents supporting the project's educational objectives.
- Partners reported progress on literature review and curriculum analysis tasks. The initial findings indicated the availability of relevant literature, though integrating all three focus areas—experience-oriented pedagogy, game-based learning, and sustainable energy education—remained challenging.

Key Outcomes:

- Developed standardized templates and instructions for literature review and curriculum comparison.
- Partners have begun synthesizing collected information to create cohesive documents that support project objectives.
- Standardized data collection methods across partners.
- Initial identification of relevant literature and curriculum details.

WP3: Framework Development

April:

- The initial assessment of development needs for the Minecraft modification was crucial. Ensuring the alignment of game mechanics with educational goals was a primary focus.
- Prepared a streamlined mod framework to support feature integration and educational goals.
- The preparation of a streamlined mod framework facilitated the integration of features and future enhancements.

May:

- Reviewing all received materials confirmed their feasibility, allowing the team to lay down the foundation for modifications. This step was essential for building a robust framework.
- Beginning the creation of graphical assets for in-game items and modes added a visual component to the educational content, enhancing engagement and understanding.

```
@Override
public void onInitialize() {

    //Adding an item to an existing vanilla item group
    /*
    ItemGroupEvents.modifyEntriesEvent(ItemGroups.TOOLS).register(content -> {
        content.add(UltiPickaxe);
    });
    */

    ModItems.RegisterModItem();
    ModBlocks.RegisterModBlocks();
    ModBlockEntities.RegisterModBlockEntities();
    ModScreenHandlers.registerScreenHandlers();

    //Adding a new item block
    Registry.register(Registries.ITEM_GROUP, new Identifier(MODID, path: "testgroup"), ToolsItemGroup);
}
```

June:

- The team expanded the workflows outlined in the design documents and continued creating graphical assets. This development phase was critical for ensuring the framework's functionality and alignment with project goals.

Key Outcomes:

- Framework preparation facilitated efficient integration of mechanics and content.
- Initial graphical asset creation and defined processes supported ongoing development.

WP4: Lesson Plan Development

April:

- Organized kickoff meeting at Linz School of Education.
- Reviewed previous lesson plans in Minecraft and STEAM literature.
- Consulted industry experts to determine relevant environmental themes and outcomes for school curricula.

May:

- Conducted a literature review using specific keywords related to Minecraft and STEAM.
- Drafted a curriculum and lesson plan example, focusing on constructivist and experiment-based learning methods.

June:

- Focused on lesson plan development, covering topics such as CO2 production and renewable resources.
- Collected 10 articles for the Game-Based Learning field and synthesized curriculum data from JKU experiences.

Key Outcomes:

- Developed initial lesson plans and educational frameworks.
- Completed a comprehensive literature review and curriculum comparison.
- Began detailed drafting of lesson plans and Game Design Document (GDD).

WP5: Dissemination and Communication

April:

- Developed a visual identity pack and created official social network pages and a YouTube channel.
- Prepared a Dissemination and Communication Plan and established a Zenodo Community account.

May:

- Updated the Communication and Dissemination Strategy based on partner feedback.
- Participated in the Europe Day Festival 2024 in Budapest for broader project dissemination.

June:

- Regularly updated the project website and improved search engine rankings.
- Continued media monitoring and engagement with the STEAMCRAFT community.

Key Outcomes:

- Established a strong visual identity and online presence.
- Actively disseminated project information through various channels and events.
- Maintained ongoing communication and engagement with stakeholders.

Next Steps

- Continue monitoring and updating the Gantt chart.
- Finalize and publish the M1-2-3 flash report and first result report on the website.
- Partners to complete their literature reviews and curriculum analyses, synthesizing findings for cohesive documentation.
- Further development of lesson plans and detailed drafting of the GDD.
- Ongoing dissemination activities to increase project visibility and stakeholder engagement.

Conclusion

The STEAMCRAFT Erasmus+ project has demonstrated significant progress and achievements over the past three months. The collaborative efforts among partners, effective project management, and strategic dissemination activities have contributed to the successful advancement of the project's

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goals. Here are the key conclusions drawn from the detailed evaluation of the project activities and outcomes:

Effective Project Management and Coordination

The project management team has successfully established clear administrative and financial protocols, ensuring smooth operations and compliance with national and European requirements. Regular meetings and updates, along with meticulous planning and monitoring, have kept the project on track. The creation of standardized templates, detailed instructions, and a comprehensive Gantt chart has facilitated efficient coordination among partners, fostering a collaborative and transparent work environment.

Comprehensive Literature Review and Curriculum Comparison

WP2 has made substantial progress in conducting literature reviews and curriculum comparisons. The development and dissemination of standardized templates and instructions have enabled partners to systematically collect and analyze data on experience-oriented pedagogy, game-based learning, and sustainable energy education. The initial results have provided valuable insights into the existing research and curriculum practices, paving the way for the development of cohesive educational frameworks.

Robust Framework Development

The framework development under WP3 has laid a solid foundation for the Minecraft modifications and educational content. The team's efforts in assessing development needs, cross-checking game mechanics, and preparing a streamlined framework have ensured that the modifications align with the project's educational objectives. The creation of initial graphical assets has added a visual dimension to the educational content, enhancing its engagement and effectiveness.

Innovative Lesson Plan Development

WP4 has focused on creating lesson plans that integrate renewable energy and environmental themes into Minecraft-based education. The comprehensive literature review and consultation with industry experts have informed the development of relevant and impactful lesson plans. The ongoing work on lesson plan development and the preparation for teacher training workshops underscore the project's commitment to providing innovative and effective STEAM education.

Strategic Dissemination and Communication

WP5 has successfully established a strong online presence and visual identity for the STEAMCRAFT project. The creation of social media platforms, a dedicated website, and a detailed Dissemination and Communication Plan has ensured effective communication and wide dissemination of project information. Participation in public events like the Europe Day Festival 2024 has significantly enhanced the project's visibility and engagement with stakeholders.

Collaborative Efforts and Future Directions

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The collaborative efforts among all partners have been a cornerstone of the project's success. The regular sharing of updates, feedback, and progress has fostered a spirit of teamwork and mutual support. Looking ahead, the project will continue to build on the foundation laid in these initial months, with a focus on completing the literature reviews, synthesizing findings, finalizing lesson plans, and preparing for the upcoming teacher training workshops. Continued dissemination and engagement activities will ensure the project's outcomes reach a wide audience and have a lasting impact.

In conclusion, the STEAMCRAFT Erasmus+ project is well on its way to achieving its objectives. The progress made in these early months highlights the project's potential to deliver innovative and impactful STEAM education using Minecraft as a central tool. The dedication and collaboration of all partners will be crucial in driving the project forward and realizing its vision of integrating experience-oriented pedagogy, game-based learning, and sustainable energy education.